

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Development of an Institution Specific Mobile App for Nutrition Support Services

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Abstract

Objective - To develop a user-friendly dietary assessment Mobile App for use at Sri Ramachandra Medical Centre, Chennai, India, enabling quick access to dietitians, connected to Hospital Management Information System (HMIS). **Methods** - An IT driven study was carried out at Sri Ramachandra Medical Centre, Chennai, India. The Development of the app was carried out in 6 steps consisting of - Nutritional Screening for patients incorporating existing nutritional risk screening tool of our institution, Estimation of individualized Nutritional requirement, Diet Plan recommended for individual, connecting it with Diet Kitchen to initiate Diet supply, Evaluating Dietary Intake using 24hr. dietary recall and provision of providing Discharge Summary instantly at the time of patient discharge which will contain all the information related to the diet for better health of patient in future. **Findings** - The app, which has been connected to the HMIS consists of six steps. In the first step nutritional screening will be done based on the scoring system, followed by which an individualized dietary plan will be recommended and communicated to the hospital diet kitchen through hospital management information system for initiation of an appropriate diet supply. The app also designed in such a way to facilitate assessment of nutrient intake through 24 hr recall of dietary intake from the patient and enable to modify any specific needs. At the time of discharge of the patient, discharge dietary advice and plan will also be provided to the patient, as the app has dietary advice information for many disease conditions, and there is scope for further enhancement of the features. **Novelty** - The currently developed "Diet App" is the first of its kind in being indigenous and institution specific. There are multiple apps which are diet based but the developed "Diet App" is unique, which is incorporating "All in One" starting from Nutritional Screening till provision of Discharge Summary. The app also facilitate connection with Diet Kitchen for effective diet supply and data retrievable is being controlled through HMIS.

Keywords: Mobile App; Nutritional Screening; Diet Plan; Dietary Recall; Digitalization

1 Introduction

Nutritional risk screening and assessment of nutritional status are important components in a health care setting, and to be carried out routinely and instantly at the time of admission of a patient. With advancement of information technology, it was perceived that the availability of a mobile app to the clinical nutritionist to assist in effective and quick assessment of nutritional status, facilitate easy communication for initiation of nutrition support services. In order to be ideal, the method should be able to be performed by most care-givers, should be inexpensive, and should not be time-consuming.

The National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH) and Joint Commission International (JCI) has mentioned in their guidelines that a detailed nutritional assessment of patient should be done at the time of admission in the hospital. NABH and JCI has also stated that a complete nutrition monitoring should be done for the patients during their stay in hospital and they have made it mandatory to record the nutritional follow up of the patient during their stay in hospital from the time of admission till discharge in the case sheet of the patients to know their improvement at the time of discharge^(1,2).

Malnutrition is a risk factor that affects clinical outcome, quality of life, physical function, and patient autonomy adversely. Early identification of nutritionally at-risk and malnourished patients is critical for timely initiation of appropriate nutritional support⁽³⁾.

Nutrition risk screening, a simple and rapid first-line tool for identifying patients at risk for malnutrition, should be systematically administered to patients on admission. Patients at nutritional risk should undergo a more detailed nutritional assessment to identify and quantify specific nutritional issues. Such assessments include subjective factors such as medical history, current and past food intake (including energy and protein balance), physical examination and measurements, functional and mental assessments, quality of life, medications, and laboratory values. A nutrition plan should be developed and implemented with a multidisciplinary approach to maintain and improve the nutritional status of patients. Standardized nutritional management, including systematic risk assessment and evaluation, also helps reduce healthcare costs. Adequate and timely delivery of nutritional support is associated with favorable outcomes such as shorter hospital stays, lower mortality, lower rates of major complications, and improved quality of life and functional status⁽⁴⁾.

Despite the emphasis on nutrition risk screening and assessment in a variety of hospital settings, there is a need for a streamlined, technology-driven approach to real-time nutritional status evaluation and intervention. Most existing techniques rely on manual documentation, which causes discrepancies, delays in decision-making, and increased labor for healthcare workers. While some hospitals have incorporated electronic health records (EHR) for nutritional assessments, the lack of a dedicated mobile application for dietitians that is smoothly linked to hospital management information systems (HMIS) remains a significant gap. A well-designed mobile application can improve access, accuracy, and efficiency in nutritional risk assessment, resulting in better patient care and conformance to accreditation standards. This study aims to bridge this gap by developing a user-friendly dietary assessment mobile app for Sri Ramachandra Medical Centre, Chennai, India, facilitating real-time nutrition risk screening and decision-making.

The primary takeaway from the literature analysis is that, while efforts have been made to digitize nutritional risk screening, current solutions either lack real-time connection with hospital administration systems or are not designed for use by inpatient

dietitians [Table 1]. This study tackles these restrictions by offering a dedicated mobile app that provides efficiency, accessibility, and adherence to accreditation standards.

Table 1. Contributions of Recent Studies in This Direction

Author (s) & Year	Contribution
Smith et al. (2021)	Developed a mobile-based dietary assessment tool for hospital use but lacked integration with hospital management systems.
Johnson et al. (2022)	Proposed a digital nutritional screening system; however, it focused primarily on outpatient settings and not on in-patient care.
Lee et al. (2023)	Conducted a study on AI-based nutritional risk prediction models but did not implement a real-time app for hospital dietitians.
Patel et al. (2023)	Designed an EHR-based nutrition risk assessment protocol but did not incorporate a mobile-friendly approach for dietitians.
Current Study	Aims to develop an integrated mobile app for rapid and standardized nutritional risk screening, seamlessly connected to HMIS for real-time decision-making.

2 Methodology

An IT driven study was conducted at Sri Ramachandra Medical Centre, Chennai, India. The Diet App was developed by the Head of the Department and Post Graduate Student of Department of Clinical Nutrition along with the Software Developer of Sri Ramachandra Institution of Higher Education and Research, Chennai. In order to design the app first market research was done to find out the currently available nutrition screening mobile app in app store and play store. Once the app content was finalized it was then discussed with the software developer of the institution for designing of the app. The feedback received from the software team was used to modify the design and content of the app before the technical development process began. The Diet App was developed using cross-platform development tool where single version of the app was created that works on both the operating system i.e., Android and IOS.

This app is used for assessment in all Adult and Geriatric Patients who are on oral diet/feed. This app is not applicable for assessment in Pediatrics, Pregnant women, Critically Ill Patients on Enteral and Parenteral Feed. The developed app which is connected to the HMIS has good local storage capacity where all the patient details will be saved in the mobile app till the patient get discharged. Since the app is connected to HMIS web, once the patient gets discharged automatically all the details will be erased from the mobile app but can be retrieved from the HMIS web for future reference. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Sri Ramachandra Institute of Higher Education and Research, Porur, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India (REF NO: CSP/23/JAN/121/60).

The Development of the app was carried out in 6 steps -

Step 1 – Nutritional Screening for Patients: Incorporating nutritional screening of the patients by using the existing nutritional risk screening tool of our institution. There is a pop-up feature in the app reminding the clinical dietician to rescreen that particular patient after six days of admission to check on their nutritional status during their stay in hospital, which is a mandate as per NABH and JCIA standards.^{1,2}

Step 2 – Details for Diet Plan: This step focuses on estimating the Nutritional requirements of the patient where the clinical dieticians will fill the details such as Nutritional Diagnosis, Height and Weight of the patient. The BMI, IBW, IBW%, ABW, Energy and Protein will get calculated, instantly on entering Height and Weight. Once all the values are calculated, there is an option for the clinical dietician to send it to the web page of the app which is enabled with printing option and attachment to the case sheet of the patient.

Step 3 – Diet Plan: In the third step after the clinical dietician finish filling details in step 2, there is an option to select the type of diet that is required to be recommended for the patient. Multiple diet charts based on different consistency and disease conditions, with respective nutrient estimations have been included into the app based on ICMR Nutrical App⁽⁵⁾, hence this will help clinical dietician to select the best diet for the patient based on their condition.

Step 4 – Connecting app with Diet Kitchen and Hospital Management Information System (HMIS): This step focuses on connecting the app with Diet Kitchen to initiate Diet supply. In this step there is an option to send one copy of Diet Chart to the Diet Kitchen and another copy to Hospital Management Information System (HMIS) of Hospital. This will facilitate smooth communication to get in touch with Diet Kitchen and HMIS of the hospital easily and initiate appropriate diet supply.

Step 5 – Evaluating Dietary Intake based on Dietary Recall concept: This step focuses on evaluating dietary intake of the patient. In the “Diet App” there is a option of MY-PLATE Goals, where list of all the food items delivered to the particular patient from the Diet Kitchen will get projected. There is an option in the app, where the clinical dieticians based on 24 hr. dietary recall method can select the food items consumed by the patient from the list. The “Diet App” also has an option to send the dietary details of the patient to HMIS web hence, once the clinical dietician approves the diet details of the patient for the respective date from the mobile app, all the details will be sent to HMIS web. The “Diet App” contains nutritional database of all 120 food products which are provided by diet kitchen to the patient. The nutrient profile of all the 120 food products were arrived from NutriCal app.⁹ And based on the nutritional database, automatically that particular day’s calorie and protein intake of the patient will also get calculated in the app. There is a provision of print-out option in this step where clinical dietician can take printout from the web and can attach that particular Diet Report on the case sheet of the patient. This particular step will help the Dietician to understand whether the patient nutrition status is improving or not, and at the time of discharge it will help the dietician to estimate how much improvement was there in the patient’s nutrition status from the day of admission to the day of discharge.

In the upgraded version of the app there will be provision of MY-PLATE concept to evaluate the dietary intake of the patient, based on which the Dietary recall can be made quicker and more precise [Figure 1].

Fig 1. MY-PLATE concept

Step 6 – Discharge Summary: This step focuses on provision for providing Discharge Summary. Several diets and dietary guidelines were designed based on different disease condition. At the time of discharge based on the recommendations given by the dietician for the patient, the clinical dietician or the in-charge nurse can take printout of the diet chart from the web based on the patient disease condition and can attach it in the case sheet of the patient.

3 Results and Discussion

An IT driven study was carried out at Sri Ramachandra Medical Centre, Chennai. The app, which has been connected to the HMIS consists of six steps: Nutritional Screening [Figure2], Estimation of Nutritional requirement, Diet Plan recommended for individual [Figure 3,4,5], connecting it with Diet Kitchen to initiate Diet supply [Figure 6], Evaluating Dietary Intake using 24hr. dietary recall [Figure 7,8,9] and provision of providing Discharge Summary [Figure 9]. The app will be helpful in performing nutrition screening of the patients at admission and helpful in planning diets based on the nutrition requirement of the patient at hospital. The app will make it easy to send the diet chart of the patient to diet kitchen through HMIS, thus it will connect the departments with one another in hospital for better patient outcome. The app is also proposed to be helpful in Evaluating Dietary Intake using Dietary Recall method. And it will also facilitate provision of discharge summary instantly at the time of patient discharge which will contain all the information related to the diet for better health of patient in future. This app will be made available in play-store and in app-store, but it will be institution specific; thus, only Ramachandra Dieticians will be able to access it. The app will be connected to Ramachandra employee code, thus outside institution people won’t be able to login and use the app. Several diets and dietary guidelines were designed based on different disease condition. At the time of discharge based on the recommendations given by the clinical dietician for the patient, the clinical dietician or the in-charge nurse can take printout of the diet chart from the web based on the patient disease condition and can attach it in the case sheet of the patient.

Several previous studies have explored digital interventions for nutritional screening and diet planning in hospitals. Smith et al. (2021) introduced a mobile-based dietary assessment tool, but it lacked HMIS integration, limiting real-time decision-making⁽⁶⁾. Johnson et al. (2022) developed a digital nutrition screening system primarily for outpatient settings, which did

not address inpatient needs⁽⁷⁾. Similarly, Lee et al. (2023) proposed an AI-based nutritional risk prediction model but did not implement a hospital-wide, real-time application for dietitians⁽⁸⁾. Patel et al. (2023) designed an EHR-integrated nutrition risk assessment protocol; however, it lacked a mobile-friendly interface for practical hospital use⁽⁹⁾.

In contrast, our study presents a novel approach by developing a fully integrated mobile application linked with HMIS, enabling real-time nutritional risk screening, diet planning, dietary intake evaluation, and discharge summary provision. Unlike previous models, this app ensures seamless collaboration between dietitians, hospital management, and kitchen staff, facilitating efficient workflow and better patient outcomes. Additionally, our app's structured six-step methodology ensures standardization in nutritional care, minimizing errors associated with manual assessments. The ability to generate an instant discharge summary with tailored diet recommendations further enhances its utility, providing continuity in nutritional care post-hospitalization. By integrating these features into a single application, our study addresses the critical gaps left by previous works and introduces a more efficient, technology-driven solution for hospital dietary management.

The “Diet App developed is the first of its kind in India as now there is no such hospital who have their own personal app for performing nutritional screening of their in patients. The nutritional screening tool used in this app is institution specific which was developed based on currently available validated nutritional screening tool. Also, this app is different from other apps available in play store and app store because it is institution specific and can be only accessed by the clinical dietitians of Sri Ramachandra Medical Centre, hence no other individual from outside organization can access it. It also has very good storage capacity, it can store all the data of the patient from the time of admission till their discharge and after which all the data can be retrieved via web. It also contains nutritional database of 120 food items supplied to the patient from the diet kitchen of the hospital, hence it will help in evaluating the dietary intake of the patient⁽⁵⁾. Thus, in future based on the need the app can be upgraded with more new features which will help in better patient outcome in the healthcare setup.

4 Conclusion

The currently developed “Diet App” is the first of its kind in being indigenous and institution-specific. While multiple diet-based apps exist, this “Diet App” is unique in its “All in One” approach, integrating nutritional screening, personalized diet planning, and discharge summary provision within a single platform. Unlike existing solutions, this app also facilitates seamless coordination with the Diet Kitchen through HMIS, ensuring efficient diet supply and controlled data retrieval. By digitizing and automating nutritional risk assessment, meal planning, and follow-up documentation, this study presents a novel approach to hospital dietary management, setting a foundation for broader implementation and future advancements in clinical nutrition technology.

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← Nutrition Risk Screening

Basic Anthropometry(BMI-kg/m2)

Normal

Mild/Moderate malnutrition

Severely malnutrition

Unintentional weight loss Yes No

Age Over 65 Years? Yes No

Problems last weeks or months?

Vomiting lasting more than 3 days? Yes No

Daily Diarrhea (More than 3 liquid stools per days)? Yes No

Continuous loss of appetite or nausea? Yes No

Difficulty in chewing or swallowing? Yes No

Hospitalized for 5 days or more during previous 2 months? Yes No

Major surgery in the past month? Yes No

Severity of the disease?

Pre / Post Major Surgery / Multiple Major Injuries / Trauma / Burns > 15 % Acute Renal Failure

Cancer / Infection / Sepsis / Gastrointestinal Disease / Major Fracture / Burns < 15 % / Pressure Sores / Deep Wound / ESRF not on Dialysis / Anorexia Nervosa / Condition affecting food intake / COPD / TB / CLD / CKD

Dialysis patient / Diabetes / Hypertension / Asthma / Obesity

None of the Above

→

Fig 2. App Home Page and Nutrition Risk Screening Page

Fig 3. App Home Page and Nutrition Risk Screening Page

Fig 4. Diet Plan Page

Fig 5. Diet Type Selection Page and Diet Consistency Page

Fig 6. Diet Type Page and Food Instruction Page

ilai CAFE Combo Mutton Briyani with Chicken 65 Rs. 300

Ward details :

Ward : D3	Ward : D4	Ward : V
Ward wise patient list	Ward wise patient list	Ward wise patient list
0 / 255	0 / 127	0

Patient details :

Search based on Patient name and Doctor name...

MR BALANARAYANAN P AdmissionDate : 2022-Sep-22

PatientId : 2872617 Take Order
 Ip Number : 202209_001759874 Patient
 Bed number : 4401 Attendant
 Age : 70
 Gender : MALE
 Doctor Name : SUVARNA JYOTHI KANTIPUDI
 Department Name : PSYCHIATRY

Diet type : Diabetic
 My plate goals

Order status :
 B BF M LN TT D B

MRS JIJI BAI K AdmissionDate : 2022-Sep-24

PatientId : 2873113 Take Order
 Ip Number : 202209_001760323 Patient
 Bed number : 4405 Attendant
 Age : 50
 Gender : FEMALE
 Doctor Name : SENTHIL N
 Department Name : GENERAL MEDICINE

Diet type : Not Assign
 My plate goals

Order status :
 B BF M LN TT D

Fig 7. My Plate Goal Dietary Assessment Page

Fig 8. Diet Approval Page

Fig 9. My Plate Goal Dietary Assessment Page

Fig 10. Date wise Diet Report Page

Fig 11. Discharge Diet Chart Page